

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

No11
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 586 sahifa,
4-noyabr, 2025-yil.

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Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

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Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

Oilaning maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar estetik tarbiyasidagi o'rni	24
<i>Abdullayeva Ma'sudaxon Abdubannayevna</i>	
Bo'lajak informatika o'qituvchilarini pedagogik faoliyatga metodik tayyorlash texnologiyalari	27
<i>Abdubannoyeva Muxlisaxon Iqboljon qizi, Abdullayev Alibek Qodiraliyevich</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida bulutli xizmatlardan foydalanish zaruriyati	30
<i>Abdullayev Alibek Qodiraliyevich, Turdaliyeva Muslimaxon Jahongir qizi</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida fortepiano chalishni o'rgatish metodikasi	34
<i>Abduvaxobova Nilufar Abdumannon qizi</i>	
Maktabda fizika fanini o'qitishda innovatsion yondashuv	38
<i>Alinazarova Mahfuza</i>	
Tasavvufdagi "komil inson" konsepsiyasining hozirgi ta'lim tizimida shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv sifatida talqini	43
<i>Aqilxonov Saidolimxon Abdurashid o'g'li</i>	
Tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonlikni shakllantirish omillari va pedagogik shart-sharoitlar	48
<i>Choriyeva Gulbaxor Shotemirovna</i>	
Robototexnika fanini o'qitishda axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanib mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish	53
<i>Elmonov Sirojiddin Mamadiyarovich</i>	
Xalqaro baholash dasturlarida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini baholash bo'yicha jahon tajribasi	58
<i>Ergasheva S. T.</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda tabiiy fanlar orqali o'quvchilarning kognitiv salohiyatini rivojlantirish	61
<i>Eshmamatova Dilnoza Jovli qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning aqliy salohiyatini oshirishda tarbiyachi mahorati	64
<i>Karimova Gulzodaxon Marufjon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak texnologik ta'lim o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishni takomillashtirish	68
<i>Hojikarimova Gulasal Tadjaliyevna</i>	
Xorijiy talabalarga o'zbek tilini o'rgatishda elektron platformalar yaratish	71
<i>Jo'rayeva Matluba</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilar uchun raqamli ta'lim muhitini modellashtirish va uning samaradorlik omillari	74
<i>Komilova Z. X.</i>	
O'qituvchi kasbiy faoliyatida muloqot madaniyati	80
<i>M. Yu. Mahkamova</i>	
Psixologiya fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va talabalarda tahliliy fikrlashni shakllantirish masalalari	86
<i>Madazizova Dilfuza Raxmatullayevna</i>	
Integrating Listening and Speaking Skills in ESP (English for Specific Purposes) Classes	90
<i>Madina Tilavova</i>	
Bolalarni maktabga tayyorlash jarayonida neyropedagogik yondashuvlar	94
<i>N. O. Saidova</i>	
Tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalarida radiologiya fanini o'qitishda raqamli texnologiyalarning metodologik roli	99
<i>Nazarova Gulchexra Shuxratdjonovna</i>	
Ijodkorlik tushunchasining mohiyati va uning ta'limdagi roli	103
<i>Ochilova Dilbar Isroilovna</i>	
Alaliyani boshqa nutqiy nuqsonlar bilan farqli xarakteristikasi	108
<i>Oripova Zilola</i>	
Ingliz tilini o'qitishda suggestopediya metodini joriy etishning samaradorligi	113
<i>Pulatova Sitora Abdurazzoq qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalari menejerlarining kasbiy-boshqaruv kompetentligi tushunchasi va uning tarkibiy qismlari	118
<i>Qarshiboyev Sharof Egamnazarovich</i>	
Koordinatsion qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishning yosh badmintonchilar texnik-taktik tayyorgarligiga ta'siri	122
<i>Qurbanova Ilmira Alisher qizi</i>	

Blended Learning	125
Quvandikova Xadicha	
Fizika darslarida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	129
Raxmanov Valijon Turdaliyevich, O'razaliyev Alijon Xasan o'g'li	
“Qurilish jarayonlari texnologiyasi” fanida loyihalash kompetentligining tarkibiy tuzilmasi va uni raqamli ta'limga moslashtirish	135
Raxmonova Nazokat Umaraliyevna	
Vitagen texnologiyalar asosida talabalar mediamentalitetini rivojlantirishda sun'iy intellekt (AI) dasturlaridan foydalanishning tahliliy modeli	140
Rustamova Nodira Rustamovna	
Talabalarda kooperativ ta'lim asosida motivatsiyani rivojlantirish usullari	145
Sitora Toshmatova	
STEAM yondashuvi asosida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ kompetensiyani shakllantirishning zaruriyati	149
Tashibekova Munajat Xoshimovna	
Musiqqa ta'limining pedagogik asoslari va metodik tizimi	153
Toshpulatova Saida Kuzibaevna	
Texnologiya fanini o'qitishda eng samarali metodlardan foydalanish	158
Turdiyeva Shahzoda Eshdavlrat qizi	
Enhancing University Students' Self-Directed Learning Through Edtech Tools	161
Ulasheva Lobar	
Fanlararo loyiha ishlarini tashkil etish orqali o'quvchilarning dizayn fikrlash salohiyatini oshirish	164
Valiyeva Nargiza Athamboevna	
Alohida ta'lim ehtiyojiga ega o'quvchilarning kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari.....	169
Xakimova Sarvinov Sharifjon qizi	
Sun'iy intellekt asosida yaratilgan ta'lim platformalari: samaradorlik tahlili va pedagogik yondashuvlar	173
Xanbabayev Xakimjon Ikramovich, Erkinov Jasurbek Hasanjon o'g'li	
Tasavvufdagi “muhosaba” va “tafakkur” amallarining o'z-o'zini refleksiya metodlari sifatida qo'llanilishi	176
Xoshimov Nuriddin Mamadaliyevich	
Milliy sport va ommaviy o'yinlarning badiiy-estetik ahamiyati.....	182
Yaxyayeva Sojida Abdurahimovna	
Ota-ona mehriining bola psixologiyasiga ta'siri	185
Yulchiyeva Shohsanam Dilshod qizi	
Nutq rivojlanishi orqada qolgan bolalarda qo'llaniladigan innovatsion usullari samaradorligi	189
Ahmedova Nargiza Muzaffarovna	
Факторы, сдерживающие развитие науки в контексте требований к диссертационным работам	193
Зайналов Жахонгир Расулович, Нурмухамедов Аббос Мамадалиевич, Шадманов Камолиддин Кажакджанович, Самигова Нодира Хамидуллаевна	
Структура и стратегии развития предметных компетенций	197
Наимова Мафтунабону Файзулложоновна	
Психологическая консультация: современная практика, задачи и перспективы развития	203
Раупова Шохида Ахроровна	
Подготовка будущих педагогов к инклюзивному обучению детей с ограниченными возможностями здоровья: задачи и перспективы	207
Сайфутдинова Насиба Нурматовна	
Формирование иноязычной грамотности у курсантов военных вузов: социально-психологические факторы.....	211
Сулейманова Нилуфар Камилловна	
O'qituvchi shaxsiy kompetensiyasining mohiyati va pedagogik faoliyatdagi o'rni	214
Abdiraxmonova Guliston Muzaffar qizi	
Bolalarda axloqiy qadriyatlarini shakllantirish jarayonining milliy va umuminsoniy tamoyillari	218
Abdumutalipova Gulshodaxon Nurbek qizi	
Fuqarolik jamiyatida huquqiy madaniyat va uni rivojlantirish jarayonlari	221
Abdusalimova Shaxnoza Quduratullayevna	
Ta'lim menejmenti tizimida o'qituvchining nutq madaniyatini rivojlantirish strategiyalari	224
Abduxalilova Iroda Nozimxonovna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS

O'zbekistonda yoshlarni ijtimoiy-pedagogik hamkorlikda tarbiyalashda "Uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya konsepsiyasi"ning ustuvor vazifalari	229
Abirova Umida Nazarovna	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini inklyuziv ta'lim sharoitida differensiyalashtirilgan dars mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishga o'rgatish (kompetentligini shakllantirish/rivojlantirish) usullari.....	232
Adhamova Diyora Sanjar qizi	
Musobaqa faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishda sambochilarning energiya sarfi va tiklanish mexanizmlari tahliliy	239
Tangriyev Abdukarim Tovashevich	
Aksiologik yondashuv asosida bo'lajak jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchilarining harakat faolligini takomillashtirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik zaruriyati.....	244
Hafizov Shahriyor Shavkatovich	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning transversal: tanqidiy va innovatsion fikrlash kompetensiyalari	248
Jaloliddinova Maftunaxon Mahmudjon qizi	
Axborotning gnoseologik mohiyati.....	256
Kamolova Munojatxon Jaloldinovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirish yo'llari	259
Mamatova Aziza Bo'riboevna	
Akademik litseylarda kimyo fanini o'qitishda raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari....	262
Maxamadiyev Sharofiddin Jumaboyevich	
Pedagogik oliy ta'limda talabalarning kasbiy ijtimoiylashuvini korporativ madaniyat asosida rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	267
Maxkamova Dilafuz Aliyevna	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilar uchun xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda lingvomadaniy yondashuv	271
Normamatova Kamola Gulmamat qizi	
O'zbek tili izohli lug'atida iboralarning grammatik tavsifi (bosh komponentli iboralar misolida).....	274
S. Sh. Azamatova	
Oila instituti va gender tenglikni ta'minlashning ijtimoiy-huquqiy muammolari	277
Salayeva Aziza Muhammadmurot qizi	
Gender yondashuv asosida talaba-qizlarda tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishning namunaviy mezonlari.....	282
Xolova Mohigul Shavkatovna	
Pedagogika yo'nalishi talabalari huquqiy savodxonligini rivojlantirish metodlarini takomillashtirish.....	287
Xudoyberganov Atham	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida leksik komponentlikni TRIZ texnologiyasi yordamida rivojlantirish	291
Zokirova Sohiba Muxtoraliyevna, Fayzullayeva Nazokat Uchqun qizi	
Цифровизация и трансформация образования как социально-педагогическое явление	295
Кадирова Наргиза Азаматовна	
Методика формирования креативного мышления у студентов-филологов на основе проблемно-ориентированных заданий (на материале английского языка)	298
Мамырбаева Дина	
Структура и стратегии развития предметных компетенций	304
Наимова Мафтунабону Файзулложоновна	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarda morfologik kompetentlikni shakllantirish	308
Ganiyeva Shodiya Azizovna	
Модель "4+1+1" как ключевой механизм в системе практической подготовки учителей музыки.....	313
Мухитдинова Малохатхон Саиджабборовна	
Tarbiya fanini o'qish samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish.....	317
Nazarova Nasiba Abdullayevna	
Tarbiyachining kasbiy psixologik xususiyatlari.....	320
Shamshetova Anjim Karamaddinovna	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda tarbiya nazariyasi va metodologiyasi	323
Bo'ronova Iroda Bo'ronovna	
Yosh dzyudochi qizlarning mashg'ulotlar jarayonida jismoniy tayyorgarligini oshirish texnologiyalari	327
Matmuratova Iroda Baxtiyor qizi	
"Odob us-solihin" asarida yoritilgan axloqiy-didaktik g'oyalar va uning pedagogik mazmuni.....	332
A. N. Nusratov	
Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini kasbiy kompetentligini takomillashtirishning metodik asoslari	336
Xolmatov Pardaboy Qoraboevich, Abdurasulova Dilnoza	

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari faoliyatida loyihalashtirishning o'rni	342
<i>Abdusattorova Go'zalxon Abdulxabib qizi</i>	
Tibbiyot va frazeologiya inson omilida	346
<i>Achilov Muzaffar Norquliyevich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida fazoviy tasavvurlarni rivojlantirishda matematikaning ahamiyati	349
<i>Mamasaidova Muhabbat Abdulalom qizi, Akbaraliyeva Marjona Xurshid qizi</i>	
Ekoestetik kompetensiyani shakllantirishning xorijiy va milliy tajribalar tahlili	354
<i>Alijonova Maftuna Maxamadjon qizi</i>	
Pedagogik jarayonda talabalarda qadriyatli munosabatlarni shakllantirish mexanizmlari	359
<i>Alikulova Muxayyo Sherovna</i>	
Ingliz ritsarlik romanlarining lingvopoetik tahlili	362
<i>Durdona Boychayeva, Aliyeva Elmira</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda estetik tarbiya berishning pedagogik asoslari	365
<i>Altibayeva Gulbaxor Majitovna</i>	
Kasbiy kompetensiya tushunchasining mazmuni mohiyati va tarkibiy tuzilmasi	369
<i>Axmadjonova Jasmira Jamshid qizi</i>	
Developing Writing Competence Among CEFR B1 and Ielts Learners Experiencing Difficulties in English Language Acquisition	374
<i>Ayturayev Majid Mavlankhanovich</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida ijtimoiy intellektni rivojlantirishning milliy qadriyatlarga asoslangan modeli	378
<i>Azamov Umarxon Yaxyoxonovich</i>	
Complications in Teaching Argumentative Speech to Students in Grades 8–9	383
<i>Buribayeva Aziza Ismatillaevna</i>	
Interfaol o'yinlar orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-emotsional ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari	386
<i>Buriyeva Aziza Nematovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning ijodiy faolligini shakllantirish	390
<i>Davronova Sevinch</i>	
O'quvchilarda milliy va umummadaniy kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda maqollardan foydalanish bo'yicha manbaalar tahlili	394
<i>Boltayeva Barno, Eliboyeva Surayyo Abdulkarim qizi</i>	
Social Roots and Psychological Consequences of Domestic Violence	399
<i>Dumarova Gulmira Kozimbekovna, Mamadaliyeva Gulmira, Sultonova Zulhayo</i>	
The Transversal-Methodical Competence of a Preschool Educator is the Foundation of Effective And Quality Education	402
<i>Ergasheva Barno Ziyavitdin kizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ta'lim-tarbiya berishning innovatsion yo'llari	406
<i>Erkinova Mehriniso Ro'ziboyevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish savodxonligini oshirish strategiyalari	411
<i>Eshonkulova Hilola Rajab qizi</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchi va o'quvchi o'rtasidagi muloqotning bilish faoliyatiga ta'siri	415
<i>Habibova Shyira Baxtiyorovna</i>	
Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida o'qish buzilishlarini aniqlash va bartaraf etish	419
<i>Ikromova Sarvinoz Siroj qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda riskologik kompetentlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari	424
<i>Jabborova Dilafuz Furqatovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda chet tili o'rganish jarayonida kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning psixologik asoslari	428
<i>Jurayeva Sug'diyona Shamsiddin qizi</i>	
Transforming Education: The Impact of Emerging Technologies on Modern Pedagogical Practices	431
<i>Kadirova Ferangiz Himmatillo qizi</i>	
Salomatlik etikasi konsepsiyasi va pedagogik madaniyat – talabalar ma'naviyati va dunyoqarashini shakllantirishdagi roli	435
<i>Kamalova Yoqutxon Bahodirovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Tarbiyachilarning kasbiy mahoratini takomillashtirish va pedagogik faoliyat samaradorligini oshirish omillari 439 Kenjayeva Dildora Terkashevna Maktab ta'lim tizimida innovatsiyalarning o'rni va ahamiyati 443 Kistabayeva Gulchexra Djurakulovna Kichik maktab yoshi davrida o'quv faoliyati va o'quv motivlarining shakllanishi 448 Latifa Zarifovna Korayeva Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimining raqamlashtirilishi: xalqaro tajriba va istiqbollar 451 Mahmudova Zulfiya Homidovna, Hoshimova Dilnoza Boymirzoevna Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini dizayn tafakkurga o'rgatishda STEAM yondashuvining didaktik imkoniyatlari 454 Mamadaminova Munisa Maxmudjon qizi, Boboxonova Shodiyona Rustam qizi Tabiatni asrash – kelajakni asrash: Buxoro misolida 459 Mardonova Saodat Muzaffarovna Bo'lajak pedagoglarda o'z-o'zini baholash kompetentligini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish 463 Meyliyeva Nafosat Gulomovna Sun'iy intellektning ta'limda kognitiv va metakognitiv jarayonlarga ta'siri 466 Murodov Ulug'bek O'tkir o'g'li Maktabgacha ta'limda inklyuziv ta'limning tashkil etilishi 470 Mustofoyeva Muhabbat Husniddin qizi The Effectiveness of Art Therapy in Working With Children Experiencing Emotional Stress 473 Nargiza Khayrullayevna Ortikova, Laziz Azizovich Normuratov Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyalanuvchilarining musiqiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari 477 Ortiqov Akmaljon Abdusalom o'g'li CLIL metodining O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida qo'llanilishi 481 Qarshiyeva Sarvinoz Ural qizi The Use of Mobile Apps to Build Vocabulary Proficiency 486 Kosimov Sunnat Ravshan ugli Yoshlar tafakkurini rivojlantirish va ma'naviyatini oshirishda tasviriy san'atning o'rni 490 Quvonchbek Abduxamidov Axborot texnologiyalari ta'sirida san'at tushunchasining o'zgarishi 494 Rajabova Laylo O'tkir qizi Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish texnologiyalari 498 Ramozonova Bahoroy Sadriddinovna Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining nutqiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlarning pedagogik asoslari 501 Yusufzoda Shabnami Yunus, Rashidova Saida Ravshonbek qizi Axborot texnologiyalarini fizika darslarida qo'llash 506 Raxmanov Valijon Turdaliyevich, O'razaliyev Alijon Xasan o'g'li Axborot xavfsizligini o'qitishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish afzalliklari 510 Raxmetova Lazzat Eshitishda nuqsonli bo'lgan bolalarning psixologik xususiyatlarining o'ziga xosligi 513 S. A. Mamatisayeva Androgogik yondashuvning integrativ metodikasi 517 Sattorova Shaxlo Axadovna Gendered Language in Uzbek and English Media Discourse 520 Sultonova Charos Iskandar kizi Maktabga tayyorlov yoshdagi bolalarda ijtimoiy ekologik dunyoqarashni shakllantirishga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar 527 Suyunova Matluba Abdusaidovna Empatiya shifokor–pasiyent munosabatida: tibbiyot talabalarining psixologik tayyorgarligi 531 Tajiboyeva Odinoxon Rustamjon qizi, Qurbonova Fotima Farhodjon qizi Modern Approaches to Teaching Grammar 534 Tuychiyev Azamat Farkhod ugli The Importance of Psychological Preparation of Preschool Children for School Education 538 Turamov Muhammadzohid Rustamjon o'g'li
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Bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachi-pedagoglarining kasbiy-axloqiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish	541
<i>Xabibullayeva Sayyoraxon Maxamadali qizi</i>	
Imkoniyati cheklangan va sog'lom bolalar faoliyatida universal ta'limning imkoniyati	544
<i>Xolmatova Sarvinoz Raxmatilla qizi</i>	
Kurashchilarning umumiy va maxsus sport tayyorgarliklari.....	548
<i>Xudoyberganov Javlonbek Soatboy o'g'li</i>	
Tayyorlov guruhi tarbiyalanuvchilarida ekologik kompetentlik tushunchalarini rivojlantirish bosqichlari.....	551
<i>Yarova Gulhayo Fazliddin qizi</i>	
Arxitektura va dizayn yo'nalishi bitiruvchilarini kasbga yo'naltirish vositasida axborot almashish jarayonlarini optimallashtirish metodikasini takomillashtirish.....	555
<i>Kuchimov M. K.</i>	
Yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining ma'naviy kompetentligini jadidlarning pedagogik qarashlari asosida shakllantirish metodikasi (Temurbeklar maktablari misolida)	559
<i>Quldashv Murodjon G'aniyevich</i>	
Лингвистическое исследование влияния социальных сетей на синтаксические изменения в языке современного поколения.....	562
<i>Шавилова Наталья Сергеевна</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisining nutq madaniyati.....	566
<i>Islamova Dilfuza Dilshodovna, Gulimbayeva Barno</i>	
Особенности гражданского воспитания обучающихся в системе "школа–маҳалля" в Узбекистане ...	570
<i>Хайдаров Шавкат Шамсиддин угли</i>	
Mantiqiy masalalarni bajarishning metodik usullari	575
<i>Tosheva Yulduz</i>	
Bo'lajak ofitserlarni harbiy-vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalashda pedagogik-psixologik omillar (jamoat xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'linmalari misolida)	579
<i>Yarmatov Akbar Normurotovich</i>	
Yosh harbiy xizmatchi ofitserlarda muloqot madaniyatini samarali shakllantirish muammosining xorijiy tadqiqotlardagi talqini	582
<i>Matyakubov Elyor Rajapovich</i>	

THE IMPORTANCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL EDUCATION

Turamov Muhammadzohid Rustamjon o'g'li

University of Business and Science

Lecturer at the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology

Abstract: This article analyzes the content, directions, and significance of the psychological preparation of preschool children for school education. The main components of psychological readiness – emotional, social, motivational, and intellectual development – are examined. The importance of effectively organizing the process of psychological preparation in preschool educational institutions is emphasized, as it ensures successful adaptation to the school environment, supports learning motivation, and promotes personal development. The necessity of close cooperation between parents and educators is also substantiated.

Key words: Preschool education, psychological preparation, emotional development, social adaptation, motivation, learning activity, child psychology, adaptation, school readiness, parent–teacher cooperation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning maktab ta'limiga psixologik tayyorgarligi mazmuni, yo'nalishlari va ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Psixologik tayyorgarlikning asosiy tarkibiy qismlari – emotsional, ijtimoiy, motivatsion va intellektual rivojlanish – yoritiladi. Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida psixologik tayyorlov jarayonini samarali tashkil etishning ahamiyati ta'kidlanadi, chunki bu bolaning maktab muhitiga muvaffaqiyatli moslashuvini, o'quv motivatsiyasining shakllanishini hamda shaxsiy rivojlanishini ta'minlaydi. Shuningdek, ota-onalar va pedagoglar o'rtasidagi hamkorlik zarurligi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktabgacha ta'lim, psixologik tayyorgarlik, emotsional rivojlanish, ijtimoiy moslashuv, motivatsiya, o'quv faoliyati, bolalar psixologiyasi, moslashuv, maktabga tayyorgarlik, ota-ona va o'qituvchi hamkorligi.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются содержание, направления и значение психологической подготовки детей дошкольного возраста к школьному обучению. Рассматриваются основные компоненты психологической готовности – эмоциональное, социальное, мотивационное и интеллектуальное развитие. Подчеркивается важность эффективной организации процесса психологической подготовки в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях, обеспечивающей успешную адаптацию ребенка к школьной среде, развитие учебной мотивации и личностного роста. Также обоснована необходимость тесного сотрудничества между родителями и педагогами.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, психологическая подготовка, эмоциональное развитие, социальная адаптация, мотивация, учебная деятельность, детская психология, адаптация, готовность к школе, сотрудничество родителей и педагогов.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has prioritized the reform of the preschool education system, improving its quality, and ensuring thorough preparation of children for school education as a key direction of state policy.

The issue of psychological preparation of preschool-aged children for school education holds significant importance in the field of education and is currently at the center of scientific and practical research. It is crucial that children adapt to the new educational environment during the school entry process, meet the demands of the learning process, and properly develop their social and emotional abilities. This is achieved through the process of psychological readiness.

Psychological readiness ensures emotional stability, social skills, internal motivation, and cognitive development necessary for a successful start to school activities. Organizing this preparation systematically and effectively in preschool institutions creates the foundation for children's successful adaptation to school, formation of learning motivation, and personal development.

Moreover, the active involvement of parents and educators, as well as their mutual cooperation in the process of preparing children for school, is a key factor in enhancing the effectiveness of these efforts. Therefore, it is essential to identify and systematize scientific approaches regarding the content, methods, and outcomes of psychological preparation.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Scientific research on the psychological readiness of preschool-aged children for school education has been actively conducted since the second half of the 20th century. In particular, the theory of developmental education developed by V.V. Davydov and D.B. Elkonin emphasized that a child's readiness for school is directly linked to stages of their psychological development [2].

Russian psychologists such as A.A. Bodalev and L.I. Bozhovich connected school readiness with a child's personal and psychological preparedness, behavioral self-regulation, and intrinsic motivation for learning [3,4].

Among Uzbek scholars, G.M. Jalolova, N. Komilova, and M. Qodirova have proposed methodological approaches to organizing psychological readiness effectively in preschool institutions. In their studies, they have experimentally demonstrated the positive impact of techniques such as play-based activities, training exercises, and art therapy on child development [5].

During the research process, key methodological principles of scientific inquiry – such as logical consistency, historicity, coherence, and objectivity – were widely applied. These principles allowed for a deep, systematic, and accurate analysis of the process of children's psychological preparation.

Several scientific methods were employed to assess children's psychological readiness for school.

First, the observation method was used to study children's behavior and engagement during play and learning activities, as well as their emotional states and social interactions, thereby assessing their level of adaptation to the school environment. This method revealed the psychological characteristics of children in their natural activities.

Second, surveys and interviews were conducted with parents and educators to collect detailed information about the child's school readiness, family environment, and pedagogical approaches. This stage helped to identify the significance of cooperation between families and preschool institutions in forming psychological readiness.

Third, the experimental method was used for an in-depth examination of psychological readiness. Training sessions were conducted and children's readiness levels were observed before and after the intervention, analyzing changes in their emotional, social, and intellectual skills. This approach made it possible to evaluate the effectiveness of psychological preparation.

In addition, diagnostic tools such as the Lüscher Color Test and Raven's Progressive Matrices were employed to assess the emotional and intellectual condition of the child. These psychological tests objectively measured the child's internal psychological state and helped identify strengths and weaknesses in school adaptation.

Overall, the combination of these methods enabled a comprehensive and in-depth study of the complex process of preparing children psychologically for school and contributed to the development of scientific and practical approaches in this field.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

During the research, data were collected through observation, surveys, and interviews. The observation method was used to study children's behavior, emotional states, and social adaptation during play and learning activities. Surveys and interviews were conducted with parents and educators to identify their attitudes toward the process of school preparation. The obtained data were analyzed using comparative, generalization, and statistical methods, which allowed for an objective evaluation of the level of children's psychological readiness for school education.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Based on the theoretical analysis and practical observations conducted during the study, it was revealed that psychological preparation of preschool-aged children for school is a decisive factor in their adaptation to the school environment, learning motivation, and personal development.

The main components of psychological readiness – emotional stability, social engagement, a positive attitude toward learning, and intellectual curiosity – were confirmed through empirical observation to be essential qualities for children entering school. The development of these traits in children largely depends on pedagogical approaches and the family environment. Results were significantly higher in groups where educators maintained consistent collaboration with parents.

Moreover, it was found that psychological readiness can be effectively developed in preschool institutions through training sessions, social games, and role-playing activities. These methods help children develop important skills such as expressing their opinions freely, solving problems, and engaging in group work.

Challenges identified during the discussion included:

- In some cases, educators lacked sufficient knowledge about psychological preparation;
- Parents showed indifference or had incorrect approaches toward the process;
- Curricular methods offered limited content regarding psychological readiness.

Key findings include:

1. A child's successful adaptation to school is closely linked to early psychological readiness.
2. Children with higher levels of psychological readiness exhibit lower levels of stress and anxiety and adapt more quickly to educational settings.
3. Psychological training and interactive methods enhance the effectiveness of preparation.
4. Active cooperation among parents, educators, and psychologists is a critical factor.

Main components of psychological readiness:

1. **Emotional and volitional readiness** – the child's ability to control emotions, express feelings, and develop inhibitory functions.
2. **Social readiness** – the ability to work in a group, communicate with peers, and understand and follow the teacher's instructions.
3. **Motivational readiness** – formation of a positive attitude and motivation toward learning.
4. **Cognitive (intellectual) readiness** – attention, memory, thinking, speech, and imagination at a level appropriate for school requirements.

Why is it important?

- Successful adaptation – psychologically prepared children experience less stress and adapt more easily to the social environment of school.
- Stable learning motivation – a strong and sustained internal interest in learning is formed early.
- Personal development – qualities such as independence, responsibility, and self-regulation develop early.
- Alignment with national education standards – children with high psychological readiness acquire educational programs more quickly and effectively.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the psychological preparation of preschool-aged children for school education is one of the most essential and critical stages in the education system. This process must be supported not only by educators but also by parents, psychologists, and all segments of society. A psychologically prepared child is able to fully realize their potential and embodies the qualities necessary for successful learning at school.

The conducted analysis and discussions have shown that children's successful adaptation to school is directly dependent on their level of psychological readiness. However, in practice, several issues have been identified – such as insufficient knowledge and qualifications of educators in this area, parental indifference or improper approaches, and the lack of adequate attention to psychological readiness in educational and methodological materials.

Children with a high level of psychological readiness experience significantly fewer stress-related situations and are able to adapt to the learning process more quickly and successfully. The use of psychological training and interactive methods in this process substantially increases the effectiveness of preparation.

Most importantly, active and integrated collaboration between parents, teachers, and psychologists plays a decisive role in the comprehensive development of the child's personality. Therefore, responsible involvement of all participants in the school readiness process, their coordinated cooperation, and the application of modern methods are of vital importance.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. №11

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.